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greater than 5%. Hence, an average of 23% of females and 8% males were misclassified based on their severity of DLCO.

In conclusion, a clinically significant difference exists between the ECSC and GLI reference equations. Respiratory departments should strongly consider changing to GLI (2017) to avoid misdiagnosis.

References

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3.3. Worrying changes in adolescent e-cigarette use 2014-2019: A secondary analysis of five Irish health datasets

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E-cigarette use is increasing worldwide. Concerns about adolescent use include harms (known and unknown), nicotine addiction, and as a “gateway” drug.

Secondary analysis was carried out on five Irish health datasets, with questions on adolescent e-cigarette, all stratified random samples in school-based settings: ECIGS-TFRI 2014 (N=817), ESPAD-TFRI 2015 (N=1508), SILNE-R-TFRI 2016 (N=2051), GUI 2017 (N=6216), ESPAD-TFRI 2019 (N=3556). We report on 16 and 17 year olds.

Descriptive statistical techniques were used to estimate changes in prevalence, reasons for trying e-cigarettes, and relationship with tobacco at first use.

Prevalence of ever-use increased from 23% in 2014 to 39% in 2019, representing a rapid increase, particularly since 2016. Curiosity (66%) and friends (29%) are now the two main reasons adolescents use e-cigarettes. Those saying they had never used tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes increased from 32% in 2015 to 68% in 2019.

E-cigarette use has risen rapidly among adolescents in Ireland since 2014. E-cigarettes are not used by adolescents for smoking cessation. The majority of adolescents who use e-cigarettes were not smokers when they started using e-cigarettes, pointing to a worrying new route into nicotine addiction. Current tobacco control regulations for young people should be extended to include e-cigarettes.

Changes in	16 year olds n (%)	17 year olds n (%)
Prevalence of e-cigarette ever-use		
<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2019	754 (38.8)	279 (37.5)

<i>GUI</i> 2017	1564 (31.3)	
<i>SILNE-R-TFRI</i> 2016	148 (31.8)	85 (50.0)
<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2015	252 (24.2)	98 (26.3)
<i>ECIGS-TFRI</i> 2014	77 (25.7)	101 (23.0)

Reasons for trying e-cigarettes

<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2019		
To quit smoking	16 (3.4)	14 (5.0)
Because friends were using it	137 (28.8)	83 (29.8)
Out of curiosity	315 (66.3)	187 (67.0)
<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2015		
To quit smoking	48 (19.2)	15 (15.5)
As an alternative to tobacco smoking	27 (10.8)	9 (9.3)
Because friends were using it	57 (22.8)	25 (25.8)
Out of curiosity	151 (60.4)	64 (66.0)

Relationship with Tobacco when first tried e-cigarettes

<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2019		
I have never smoked tobacco	461 (66.7)	149 (58.7)
I smoked tobacco occasionally	168 (24.3)	83 (32.7)
I smoke tobacco regularly	57 (8.9)	22 (8.7)
<i>SILNE-R-TFRI</i> 2016		
I have never smoked tobacco	10 (19.6)	0 (0.0)
I have tried tobacco but don't use it regularly	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
I smoked tobacco occasionally/regularly	-	-
<i>ESPAD-TFRI</i> 2015		
I have never smoked tobacco	76 (32.2)	31 (34.1)
I smoked tobacco occasionally	123 (52.1)	42 (46.1)
I smoke tobacco regularly	37 (15.7)	18 (19.8)

Table 1. Changes among Irish 16 and 17 year olds between 2014 and 2019 in prevalence of e-cigarette ever-use, reasons for trying e-cigarettes, and relationship with tobacco when first trying e-cigarettes

Figure 1: Trend of e-cigarette prevalence between 2014 and 2019

Conflicts of interest: None

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